

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART II. SYNTHESIS
OF SOME ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY RICINUS LIPASE
FROM CASTOR SEEDS

BY G. V. NEVGI AND C. V. RAMAKRISHNAN

Syntheses of some aliphatic esters by ricinus lipase have been carried out in order to study the effect of change of the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol on the enzymic synthesis of esters.

Bodenstein, Dietz and Dietz (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1906, 12, 605) investigated the formation and the splitting of *isoamyl* butyrate by pancreatic lipase. Rona and Ammon (*Biochem. Z.*, 1931, 241, 460) synthesised *n*-butyl normal butyrate by pig's pancreatic lipase. Since much work has not been done on the synthetic activity of the seed lipase, an attempt was made to study the synthesis of some aliphatic esters using ricinus lipase from castor seeds.

Synthesis of Butyl Oleate using Different Samples of Lipase.—Velluz (*Bull. soc. chim. Biol.*, 1939, 21, 814) synthesised butyl oleate using petroleum ether-dried lipase in 17 organic solvents. In the present work, the synthesis of butyl oleate was carried out with different solvents such as petroleum ether, carbon tetrachloride, ether, etc., and the mixture was observed to be homogeneous only in ether solvent. As all the work was carried out with a view to ascertaining the effect of the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol and the acid on the synthesis and hydrolysis of esters, ether was chosen as a solvent for all the experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were (1) butyl alcohol (d 0.809, b.p. 117°), (2) oleic acid (d 0.895, b.p. 286°). In different conical flasks, 5 c.c. of the acid and 3 c.c. of alcohol were added. One gram of lipase and 10 c.c. of the solvent were added to each flask, shaken well and kept in the incubator after corking them well. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion from each flask was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed for some time and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. Always the blank accompanied the sample. From the difference in readings between the sample and the blank, the percentage synthesis was calculated. The same experimental procedure was adopted for the rest of the work. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Solvent: Ether.

Days.	Percentage synthesis of butyl oleate		
	French author.	Present work using petroleum ether sample.	acetone sample.
1	17.8	18.9	6.4
2	31.2	34.8	15.6
3	42.7	43.2	21.6
4	53.4	50.8	32.8
5	56.7	59.5	39.6
6	60.7	70.2	38.5

From the above table, it is found that the results obtained in case of petroleum ether-dried lipase almost agree with those of the French author within the limits of experimental error. The same synthesis, when carried out using acetone-dried lipase, gives the low value. For the rest of the work, acetone-dried lipase was used since it kept its activity fairly constant for an appreciably long time even though the percentage synthesis was low.

Synthesis of some Aliphatic Esters.—The synthesis of the following esters belonging to a homologous series was carried out using acetone-dried lipase in ether solvent in order to study the effect of change of the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol on the synthesis of esters by lipase: methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *iso*propyl, *n*- and *iso*butyl, *n*- amyl propionates and butyrates.

Each flask contained equimolecular quantities (0.054 g. mol.) of alcohol and acid, lipase (1g.) and 10 c.c. of the solvent, and incubated at 37°. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. of it was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. Always a blank accompanied the sample. From the difference in readings, the percentage synthesis was calculated. The results are given in Tables II and III.

TABLE II

Percentage synthesis on the

Esters.	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
Methyl propionate	4.2	4.9	6.2	10.1	11.6	—
Ethyl "	5.1	6.3	10.8	15.4	17.2	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	5.5	6.6	9.1	14.6	16.8	18.3
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	12.3	19.1	32.8	25.4	27.6	—
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	12.5	15.6	21.7	28.2	28.1	29.2
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	15.2	25.3	31.6	39.5	43.9	65.4
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	45.1	55.7	71.2	77.2	76.6	—

TABLE III

Esters.	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
Methyl butyrate	3.28	4.51	6.97	9.0	11.5	—
Ethyl "	3.20	4.21	11.60	16.6	16.6	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	3.25	4.60	8.20	9.2	15.8	10.9
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	11.44	18.04	21.76	22.8	26.8	—
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	11.30	13.30	14.60	20.5	24.5	22.3
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	14.70	23.40	33.30	42.9	68.4	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	30.60	55.00	61.90	69.3	78.1	—

From Tables II and III, it is found that in case of propionates as well as butyrates, the maximum percentage synthesis increases from methyl to amyl ester. It shows that as the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol increases, the synthesis also increases up to amyl ester.

The synthesis is greater in the *iso* form of the alcohol than in the normal one. The difference in percentage synthesis in the case of *n*-propyl and *isopropyl* esters may be due to the difference in structure (*n*-propyl alcohol is primary, whereas *isopropyl* alcohol is secondary). This proves the fact that the difference in chemical reaction is observed in the case of primary and secondary alcohols. In case of normal and *isobutyl* esters, the difference in percentage synthesis may be due to the difference in density, since the structure is the same for both the esters (*n*-butyl alcohol, d 0.809; *isobutyl* alcohol, d 0.812).

Synthesis of n-Butyl and n-Amyl Esters.—Butyl and amyl esters of formic, acetic, propionic and butyric acids were synthesised using acetone-dried lipase from castor seeds, and the results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Esters.	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
<i>n</i> -Butyl formate	12.8	16.2	22.5	25.6	27.2	—
acetate	11.8	14.5	16.2	22.6	25.4	—
propionate	12.5	15.6	21.7	26.2	28.4	29.2
butyrate	11.2	13.3	14.8	20.5	24.5	28.3
<i>n</i> -Amyl formate	32.4	40.8	63.8	75.8	78.2	—
acetate	26.1	32.1	39.7	74.5	82.9	—
propionate	45.1	55.7	71.2	77.2	78.6	—
butyrate	30.6	55.0	64.9	69.3	78.1	—

From the above table, it is found that the percentage synthesis is almost the same in case of all the four esters, the difference being very small, even though the different acids are used. So, it can be concluded that the synthesis of esters is independent of the number of carbon atoms in the acids and only depends upon the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol. In Table IV, the percentage synthesis of the last four esters is always greater than that of the first 4 esters, which proves that the percentage synthesis depends upon the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol.